

Interview on the development of SNOPI

This study is being carried out in the context of doctoral research by student Alexandre Adler Cunha de Freitas, carried out in the Graduate Program in Informatics at the Federal University of Espírito Santo, under the guidance of professors Monalessa Perini Barcellos and Ricardo de Almeida Falbo (in memory).

The purpose of the interview is to investigate, from the developer's point of view, whether the use of (an extract of) HCI-ON helped in the development of an AUI (Adaptive User Interface) system. In line with this objective, we define two main questions:

(RQ1) How does using (an extract of) HCI-ON help in the development of an AUI system?

(RQ2) What are the benefits and pitfalls of using (an extract of) HCI-ON in developing an AUI system?

Each research question was divided into more specific questions to be answered by the SNOPI developer in an interview.

After accepting this consent form, some questions will be presented. The confidentiality of the individual data provided in the study is guaranteed. Data is for research purposes and is not used for personal or professional evaluation. Name (optional) and e-mail of the participants are requested only for contact purposes, in case there is a need to clarify any of the answers.

Despite being invited, participation in the study is voluntary, and they may at any time refuse to participate or withdraw from the study.

By clicking "Next", I declare that I am over 18 years old and that I voluntarily participate in this study, having read the information contained in this term before participating.

alexandre.a.freitas@edu.ufes.br (não compartilhado)

[Alternar conta](#)

*Obrigatório

E-mail *

alexandre.a.freitas@edu.ufes.br

Próxima

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Nunca envie senhas pelo Formulários Google.

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